

CAMPUS FIRE SAFETY RIGHT-TO-KNOW ACT: A SOCIOTECHNICAL ANALYSIS OF POLICY IMPACT AND INSTITUTIONAL READINESS

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzes the proposed Campus Fire Safety Right-to-Know Act, which seeks to mandate higher education institutions to disclose fire safety measures in campus buildings. Despite being introduced multiple times between 2007 and 2022, the bill has yet to be enacted into law. As campus fire incidents continue to rise, this research examines the bill's significance, challenges, and potential impact on fire emergency preparedness and campus safety. Using the sociotechnical system framework, this qualitative study gathered insights from twenty-two (22) experts in fire safety governance, disaster risk reduction, legal studies, and policymaking. Findings highlight nine (9) key factors influencing the bill's passage: limited awareness, fire safety impact, legislative value, financial constraints, disclosure challenges, proposed revisions, legislative prioritization, stakeholder collaboration, and campus preparedness, all of which are crucial for effective implementation and institutional compliance.

Keywords: *Campus Fire Safety Right-to-Know Act, Fire Safety, Proposed Bill*

INTRODUCTION

Fire-related incidents remain a pressing concern, causing sudden property destruction and loss of lives. These fires often stem from household hazards such as electrical wiring, candles, and appliances, while workplace risks include combustible materials, faulty equipment, and cluttered spaces. Schools and universities are equally vulnerable due to

electrical appliances, kitchen fires, and unsafe handling of flammable materials, sometimes leading to explosions when left unsupervised (Koorsen Fire & Safety, 2020).

The Philippines has seen a rise in fire incidents, with a 13% increase in the first two months of 2022 compared to the same period in 2021. Investigations by the Bureau of Fire Protection (BFP) attribute this surge to negligent electrical wiring use and poor fire safety measures. Given the global rise in temperatures, BFP urges the public to adopt stricter fire prevention practices (Caliwan, 2022).

Educational institutions have experienced significant fire incidents, demonstrating the urgency of safety reforms. In 2019, Kakidduguen Elementary School in Nueva Vizcaya lost seven classrooms to fire, forcing students to use makeshift tents and communal spaces (Martin, 2019). In 2021, Jose P. Laurel High School in Tondo suffered Php500,000 in damages due to a fire on its third floor (Cabanban, 2021). More recently, in 2022, West City Elementary School in Dumaguete sustained Php50,000 in damages, reportedly caused by an overheated electric fan left unplugged (Brier, 2022).

The Fire Code of the Philippines

The Fire Code of the Philippines has undergone key developments to strengthen fire safety regulations. Proclamation No. 115-A (1966) established Fire Prevention Month in March to raise awareness. In 1977, Presidential Decree No. 1185 was enacted in response to rising fire-related deaths and property damage, fostering civic involvement in fire prevention. This decree was later repealed by Republic Act 9514 (2008), which aimed to enhance public safety and economic stability by minimizing fire incidents.

The Implementing Rules and Regulations (IRR) of RA 9514 were revised in 2019 to address critical safety concerns, including occupant load factors in hospitals and fire standards for daycare centers and industrial facilities. Given the increasing fire risks, particularly in educational institutions, policymakers must prioritize legislative action to ensure campus fire safety measures are effectively implemented (Koorsen Fire & Safety, 2020; Caliwan, 2022; Martin, 2019; Brier, 2022).

Fire Incident inside University of the Philippines Campuses

The University of the Philippines (UP) has experienced multiple campus fire incidents, affecting its Diliman, Los Baños, and Cebu campuses.

One of the most tragic events occurred on May 2, 2022, when a fire broke out in Barangay UP Campus, at 5:20 AM, reaching the second alarm in minutes. The fire, caused by an electrical outlet, resulted in eight fatalities, displaced 250 families, and caused Php150,000 in property damage (Fernandez, 2022).

Similarly, on March 8, 2018, the UP Shopping Center in Diliman caught fire due to faulty electrical wiring, reaching a second alarm at 7:36 AM. Although no casualties were recorded, stall owners suffered property losses (Patena & Montemayor, 2018).

Another significant fire happened on April 1, 2016, at the UP Diliman Faculty Center, burning for over six hours, causing Php3 million in damages (CNN Philippines, 2016). Fires in the UP Alumni Center (2015), Palma Pavilion II (2010), and Narra Residence Hall (2008) were also linked to electrical hazards (Barnes, 2016).

Beyond Diliman, UP campuses elsewhere also faced fire incidents. UP Cebu experienced a fire on June 2, 2020, affecting its canteen due to faulty wiring, while UP Los Baños' Dairy Training Research Institute suffered a fire on July 8, 2020, caused by overloaded electrical lines (Cinco, 2020; UPC PIO, 2020).

The recurrence of these fires underscores the urgency of enhanced campus fire safety measures to prevent future incidents. Below is the summary of UP fire incidents:

Table 1 <i>Author's consolidation of major fire incident at UP campuses from 2008-2022</i>			
Date	Time	Place	Findings
May 05, 2022	05:20 am	UP Village	Faulty electrical wiring
Jun 02, 2020	03:00 am	UP Cebu Canteen	Faulty electrical wiring
Jul 08, 2020	03:00 pm	UPLB DTRI	Overloaded electrical lines
Mar 08, 2018	07:36 am	UPD Shopping Center	Faulty electrical wiring
Apr 01, 2016	01:20 am	UPD 3 rd floor office	Faulty electrical wiring
Jul 01, 2015	11:37 pm	UPD Alumni Center	Faulty electrical wiring
Jun 13, 2015	09:45 am	UPD CASAA Food Center	Exploded LPG
Jun 09, 2010	11:00 pm	UPD Chemistry	Hazard Chemicals
Jan 09, 2008	04:15 am	UPD Narra Residence	Faulty electrical wiring

The researcher was able to obtain pertinent data from the BFP National Headquarters, wherein the Regional Offices were requested to submit the relevant information requested on the total fire incidents in universities and colleges across Regions 1 to 12 in line with the purpose of this study; thus, the researcher was able to suffice significant data on this

research; used as a secondary data source, and was able to confirm the said incidents and causes. Below is the report obtained from the BFP:

Table 2		
Consolidated report from the National Headquarters BFP from 2007-2022		
Rank	Region	Number of Campus Fire Incident
1	Region 7 (Cebu)	66
2	NCR	48
3	Region 6 (Capiz)	27
4	Region 11 (Davao)	25
5	Region 5 (Albay)	18
6	Region 10 (Iligan)	18
7	Region 1 (Ilocos)	15
8	BARMM (Lanao)	15
9	Region 3	12
10	Region 9 (Zamboanga)	12
11	Region 12 (Cotabato)	12
12	Region 4A	09
13	Region 8	09
14	Region 2 (Tuguegarao)	08
15	CAR (Baguio)	08
16	Region 4B	05
17	CARAGA (Butuan)	02
	Total	309

Campus Fire Safety Regulations: A Myriad of Proposed Bills

The increasing frequency of campus fire incidents highlights the necessity for fire safety regulations. Various bills have been proposed in the Philippine Congress, aiming to mandate the disclosure of fire safety measures in educational institutions.

- Senator Miriam Defensor Santiago introduced Senate Bills 1131 and 2628 in 2007, establishing fire safety reporting requirements for higher education institutions.
- House Bill 2478 (2010), proposed by Representative Marcelino Teodoro, mirrored Santiago's bills with only minor revisions.
- House Bill 823 (2010) by Representatives Diosdado and Gloria Arroyo expanded the scope to include both public and private institutions, enforcing annual reporting to Commission of Higher Education (CHED) and Department of Education (DepEd).
- In 2013, the Arroyos refiled their proposal as House Bills 310, 1387, and 2959, maintaining the same provisions.
- Representative Alfred Vargas introduced House Bill 2959 (2016) following major fires at UP Diliman and University of the East, stressing stricter safety oversight.
- House Bill 1744 (2018) by Representative Luis Raymund Villafuerte Jr. responded to fatal mall fires in Davao and Cebu, shifting focus to student safety.
- House Bill 8809 (2021), revived by Magdalo Party-List Representative Manuel Cabochan III, incorporated recent fire incidents, further reinforcing the urgency of campus fire prevention.

Despite repeated filings, these bills remain stalled due to policy prioritization issues, legislative delays, and lack of urgent political will. Advocacy efforts and public awareness are essential to accelerate passage and implementation. To sum up, the fourteen (14) cited proposed senate and house bills were the progression of how the compulsory disclosure of standards and measures on fire safety involving campus buildings have been floating in congress. To wit, the said bill has already been transferred to numerous names of government officials, and from the initial scope of the higher education institutions, it developed to cover the entire educational system from public to private universities under the CHED.

Research Questions

With campus fire safety concerns becoming increasingly urgent in higher education, this study examines the risks and regulatory challenges. Key research questions include:

1. How acceptable are the bill's provisions under Republic Act 9514 to regulatory authorities and the academe?
2. What are the potential impacts of the bill on university fire safety policies, infrastructure, and operations?
3. What measures can be implemented to support and facilitate the bill's passage into law?

Research Objectives

This study aims to analyze the bills proposed concerning the compulsory disclosure of standards and measures on fire safety involving campus buildings. The following are the specific objectives:

1. To evaluate how regulatory authorities and academia perceive the feasibility of the proposed bills within the framework of republic act 9514.
2. To examine the potential effects of the bill on campus safety policies, operations, and infrastructure.
3. To identify necessary actions to support the passage and implementation of campus fire safety regulations.

Significance of the Study

Despite the critical need for campus fire safety regulations, the proposed bill has yet to be enacted due to slow legislative processes, repeated submissions with minimal revisions, and a lack of urgency from policymakers. The bill's rationale is not fully realized, leading to its low prioritization in government agendas. Without detailed fire safety disclosure, schools, colleges, and universities remain vulnerable, leaving stakeholders unaware of risks when choosing an institution. Implementing these measures would help reassess fire safety policies, create preventative interventions, and improve campus preparedness. This study highlights the importance of fire safety in higher education, critically reviews the Campus Fire Safety Right-to-Know Act, and urges policymakers to recognize the unique fire hazards in campus environments, ensuring fire and life safety systems reach legislative approval.

Limitation of the Study

This study is confined to a higher education institution setting, focusing on a specific site within the Municipality of Los Baños in Laguna. Therefore, further research is necessary to expand upon these findings.

Theoretical Framework

Considering the broadness of this framework, a particular viewpoint according to Meacham & van Straalen (2017) introduced the Sociotechnical System (STS) framework. The STS specifically focused on the three levels: primary work systems, whole organization systems, and macrosocial systems, which includes in communities and industrial sectors, and institutions operating at the overall level of society. As used here, Meacham & van Straalen (2017) STS framework provides a model for describing the actors and interaction in the building regulatory system. In this framework, there are consideration of the impact of policy adoption and the implementation decision-making process.

Figure 1

Framework for sociotechnical decision-making by Meacham & van Straalen (2017)

The International Fire Safety Standards (2020) outline a framework with two dimensions: legislation, which enforces fire safety policies, and application, which determines safety throughout a property's life cycle. A relevant theory explaining the prolonged enactment of bills like the Campus Fire Safety Right-to-Know Act is the elite theory. It argues that policymaking reflects the interests of the governing and non-governing elite, influencing legislative priorities (Anyebe, 2018). In the Philippine governance structure, elite control is evident, shaping policy decisions through hierarchical relationships. Legislators often prioritize bills based on mutual interests and political alliances, delaying fire safety reforms (Brillo, 2011). Thus, the elite theory serves as a theoretical lens for understanding legislative processes, illustrating how bills are introduced, stalled, and eventually enacted into law.

Conceptual Framework

This study employs a framework that incorporates organizational, technical, and human aspects. It integrates policy review, fire prevention infrastructure, and human engagement, aligning with the STS framework.

Figure 2
Integrated Sociotechnical Framework for Campus Fire Safety

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a descriptive qualitative research design. Qualitative content analysis was deemed significant in obtaining data that is unobtrusive, replicable and transparent,

and also highly flexible (Luo, 2019). The study site was conducted within the Municipality of Los Baños in Laguna. The research site has three campuses, namely; Laguna State Polytechnic University (Los Baños Campus), Colegio De Los Baños and UP Los Baños campus (UPLB). This is one of the first-class municipalities in the province of Laguna. Another reason for choosing the study site given the first-hand experience in campus fire reported by the BFP Los Baños station. In UPLB for example, there were three fire incidents on campus. The old Chemistry Building (now the College of Arts and Sciences Annex) in 1990, the Senior's Social Garden sometime in 1994, and the fire that gutted the Dairy Training and Research Institute (DTRI) Building in 2020. In addition, the researcher was currently residing and working inside the UPLB campus and given the actual experience in campus fire. Furthermore, the researcher was part of the first responder in attempting to control the fire and managing the flow of incoming fire trucks in the vicinity of the DTRI Building.

Methods of Data Gathering

Questionnaires was tailored and drafted accordingly for the different sets of participants for the interviews and FGDs through the timeline deemed fit with the availability of the respondents; all adhering to the ethical considerations of conducting study and data collection.

This qualitative study used focus group interviews for data collection, selecting participants through purposive sampling from colleges, universities, Local Government Units - Disaster Risk Reduction Management (DRRM) offices, and BFP representatives in Los Baños, Laguna. The academe provided insights based on first-hand campus fire experience and expertise in DRRM, safety, and public policy, while DRRM and BFP officials contributed knowledge on fire safety regulations and disaster response. Discussions focused on bill acceptability, legislative delays, and improvement areas.

RESULTS

The FGD assessed the acceptability of the Campus Fire Safety Right-to-Know Act by examining respondents' familiarity, perceptions of fire safety, and its importance. A 5-point Likert scale helped measure their agreement and awareness. Below are the nine thematic analyses of responses and their implications.

Limited Familiarity with the Bill

The majority of participants, including the BFP personnel displayed limited familiarity with the proposed bill, rating their awareness between 1 and 2 on a scale of 1 (very unfamiliar) to 5 (very familiar). This indicates that the bill is relatively unknown among these individuals from the BFP, the agency that has exclusive jurisdiction or authority over the implementation of the fire safety code suggesting a potential need for greater awareness and information dissemination. A few respondents from the academe, demonstrated moderate familiarity with ratings ranging from 3 to 5. This suggests that some individuals within the academe are more informed about the bill, although there is no unanimous awareness.

Figure 4
Graph depicting the limited familiarity with the bill

Table 3
Qualitative interpretation of being unfamiliar with the proposed bill

Office	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
BFP	1.80	Very Unfamiliar
LSPU	1.00	Very Unfamiliar
CDLB	3.14	Somewhat Familiar
UPLB	2.20	Unfamiliar
Total	2.04	Unfamiliar

Contribution to Common Fire Safety Principles

Respondents predominantly expressed strong agreement regarding its potential contribution to common fire safety principles on campuses. This indicates that they viewed the bill's provisions positively in terms of enhancing fire safety.

Figure 5
Graph depicting the strong agreement regarding the bill's potential contribution in terms fire safety

Table 4
Qualitative interpretation which the respondents predominantly expressed strong agreement with the proposed bill

Office	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
BFP	4.80	Strongly Agree
LSPU	3.80	Strongly Agree
CDLB	4.43	Agree
UPLB	4.60	Strongly Agree
Total	4.41	Strongly Agree

Perceived Importance of the Bill

Most participants, regardless of familiarity, rated the bill as important or very important, highlighting its significance for campus fire safety. A small minority rated it lower, indicating varying perspectives. One academic respondent, unfamiliar with the bill, rated it very unimportant, suggesting that lack of awareness influenced the response

Figure 6
Graph depicting the perceived importance of the bill

Table 5
Qualitative interpretation which the respondents perceived the importance of the bill

Office	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
BFP	5.00	Very Important
LSPU	4.20	Very Important
CDLB	3.86	Important
UPLB	4.20	Very Important
Total	4.31	Very Important

FGD participants generally viewed the Campus Fire Safety Right-to-Know Act as important, with familiar respondents showing stronger support for its impact. A minority expressed reservations, highlighting the need for awareness efforts. Overall, there is broad receptiveness to the bill among academic and regulatory communities, supporting its potential adoption.

Financial Concerns and Budget Allocation

Participants raised concerns about the financial challenges universities face in complying with the bill. They emphasized the need for budget allocation, particularly for sprinklers, fire hydrants, fire extinguishers, and training. Smaller colleges may struggle due to limited funds reliant on enrollment. Some noted the lack of budget provisions in the bill, complicating implementation. Despite financial hurdles, many believe compliance is crucial for campus fire safety and advocate for proper funding and support.

Difficulty to Comply with Public Disclosure of Fire Safety Standards

Some respondents found reporting fire incidents challenging, particularly Section 3, which mandates disclosure of casualties, injuries, and fire safety requirements. Compliance with sprinkler systems and safety devices was seen as difficult. Others emphasized the need for systematic data compilation.

Conversely, some participants found no problematic provisions, viewing the bill as well-structured. They noted existing fire safety protocols, such as alarms, extinguishers, and escape routes, making compliance feasible. Overall, the bill was positively received, with concerns primarily focused on reporting and implementation challenges.

Suggested Minor Revisions of the Bill

Respondents suggested revising provisions to ease financial and administrative burdens on educational institutions while ensuring fire safety compliance. Faculty members emphasized coordination with BFP and LGUs for inter-campus fire drills. External challenges include funding constraints, regulatory compliance, and reporting complexities, highlighting the need for comprehensive support to facilitate implementation while maintaining safety standards.

Legislative Prioritization and Other Factors

The Campus Fire Safety Right-to-Know Act faces legislative challenges, requiring prioritization in the Senate and House of Representatives to ensure proper discussion and funding. Faculty members emphasize its importance for teacher and student safety and suggest government fund allocation to support smaller schools struggling with compliance.

Recommendations include forming a technical working group, conducting stakeholder consultations, and securing academic sector support. Additionally, incorporating external factors such as institutional surroundings and public awareness would strengthen fire safety implementation. A holistic approach is necessary for legislative success and effective campus fire prevention.

Stakeholder Engagement and Advocacy

Stakeholder engagement and advocacy are crucial in advancing the Campus Fire Safety Right-to-Know Act. Teachers and parents strongly support the bill, emphasizing campus safety. To secure broader approval, legislators must address opposing views through dialogue and compromise, ensuring provisions benefit all stakeholders.

Effective advocacy involves persuading policymakers, academic institutions, and government agencies, demonstrating how fire safety regulations will protect campuses and improve preparedness. By fostering strategic collaboration and transparent communication, the bill's passage can gain momentum, reinforcing democratic lawmaking for public safety.

Assessment of Campus Capabilities

Assessing campus capabilities is crucial for the Campus Fire Safety Right-to-Know Act, focusing on institutions' infrastructure and budget for compliance. Older buildings may require retrofitting, demanding financial resources. Institutions must evaluate whether they can allocate budgets for fire code standards, with potential government assistance for those struggling. Beyond compliance, the bill impacts architectural planning and future institutional development by prioritizing fire safety. Stakeholder discussions reveal three key themes: legislative prioritization, campus capability assessment, and advocacy, all essential for the bill's passage and successful implementation

Table 6
Summary of qualitative interpretation

Scale	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
First time encountering the proposed bill or the proposed Campus Fire Safety Right-to-Know Act	2.04	Unfamiliar
Contribution of the requirement to the common principles of fire safety	4.41	Strongly Agree
Importance of the bill	4.31	Very Important

DISCUSSION

The acceptability of the bill correlates with participants' familiarity (State et al., 2017). While awareness varied, most respondents recognized its importance for campus fire safety. Legislative prioritization is essential for passage in Congress, ensuring proper discussion and funding (Park & Hassari, 2021). Campus capability assessment evaluates infrastructure readiness, financial constraints, and the need for government support (Chen, 2023; Xu et al., 2021). Stakeholder engagement and advocacy involve negotiating win-win provisions to gain broader support (Paraiso, 2022).

Using the sociotechnical regulatory system framework (Meacham & van Straalen, 2017), legislative priorities should be embedded in the fire code, ensuring transparent communication for compliance. Proper legislation and fire safety standards—with shared accountability—are crucial for effective implementation.

Conclusions

The FGD responses reveal that the bill's acceptability is influenced by participants' familiarity with its content. Regardless of familiarity, most participants perceived the bill as important for enhancing fire safety on campuses. To facilitate the bill's passage, it is crucial to prioritize it within the legislative agenda and consider other factors.

Assessing campus capabilities is essential to understand the readiness of institutions to comply, and stakeholder engagement and advocacy are necessary for building support and addressing opposition. These themes collectively provide a comprehensive view of the challenges and opportunities surrounding the "Campus Fire Safety Right-to-Know Act" and offer valuable insights into its potential impact and the measures needed for its successful passage.

Recommendations

To improve fire safety on campuses and support the passage of the *Campus Fire Safety Right-to-Know Act*, the following steps are essential:

1. Technical Revisions and Legislative Prioritization

- Regularly evaluate campus fire safety measures and equipment.
- Strengthen government commitment to prioritize the bill's passage.
- Address factors affecting legislative prioritization.
- Launch an awareness campaign targeting academic institutions and stakeholders.

2. Stakeholder Engagement and Policy Advocacy

- Encourage active participation from key groups to mobilize support.
- Highlight how the bill strengthens campus fire safety standards.
- Foster dialogues between supporters and opposition groups.
- Provide clear information through accessible communication channels.

3. Key Stakeholders in Policy Advocacy

- *Interest Groups*: Mobilize public and legislative support.
- *Experts & Resource Persons*: Offer recommendations for improvement.
- *Fire & DRRM Authorities*: Provide technical advice for implementation.
- *Lawmakers*: Advocate and sponsor the bill in Congress.
- *Campus Administrators*: Address safety gaps and support policy reforms.

This approach ensures the bill's successful enactment and implementation. This study emphasizes fire safety advocacy, legislative prioritization, and stakeholder engagement to enhance campus preparedness and policy implementation efforts effectively.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This paper is authored by single individual who adheres to ethical standards. The author obtained respondents' consent while conducting this survey, clearly explained the study's purpose, and ensured the confidentiality of their identities.

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